

RESEARCH NOTE

A CONTEXT-DEPENDENT ILLUSION IN THE PERCEPTION OF VELOCITY

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Abstract—It has so far been assumed that velocity contrast effects can be explained by local lateral inhibition processes which act to enhance the difference in velocity between a target and its immediate surround. A new velocity illusion is here reported that seriously questions this notion.

Motion perception Velocity illusions Translatory motion Contrast/assimilation Lateral inhibition

INTRODUCTION

In most visual domains, the perceptual properties of an object appear to be rather obviously affected by the properties of objects nearby. Sometimes differences will be enhanced, and the object will stand out more clearly against its surround. Sometimes differences will be minimized, and the object will tend to blend with its surround. Occasionally, however, an object will be influenced by its context in a much less straightforward way. One might like to take the Benary cross as an illustration of this notion in the brightness domain.

The Benary cross (Benary, 1924), shown in Fig. 1(A), is a black cross on a white field, featuring two identical gray right triangles in strategic locations. The first triangle sits on the cross and its hypotenuse borders on the white surround. The second triangle lies on the surround, fitting one of the four underarms (so to speak) of the cross in such a way that its hypotenuse also borders on the white field. Locally, therefore, the triangles are surrounded by black and white in the same proportions; yet, the triangle sitting on the cross looks distinctly lighter.

After having been treasured by the Gestalt psychologists and sunk subsequently into oblivion, this effect was recently re-proposed in a version in step with the times (White, 1979, 1981; McCourt, 1982). In the pattern investigated by White, and reproduced in Fig. 1(B), the illusion is generated in a square-wave grating in which

sections of the bars are replaced by mid-gray patches. The effect is still there if elongated gray patches are used that turn out to be surrounded by more white than black when interrupting black bars (and looking lighter) and by more black than white when interrupting white bars (and looking darker). The perceptual outcome is the opposite of what would be expected on the basis of brightness contrast. Phenomena like this clearly mark the existence of a problem with the traditional local contrast explanation; in the case in point, the hint is that more is going on.

Contrast processes are known to manifest themselves in several other domains; perception of velocity, for example. Loomis and Nakayama (1973) reported that when two targets travel at the same speed against a field of moving dots having a horizontal gradient of velocity, the target which is traveling faster than its immediate surround appears to have a larger absolute velocity than the target which is traveling slower than its immediate surround. There is little doubt that this illusion resembles rather neatly the classical simultaneous brightness contrast. Likewise, a separate effect has been reported by Walker and Powell (1974) which might be thought of as a sort of Mach band phenomenon in the velocity domain. The effect is generated in a display made up of six parallel horizontal rows of drifting dots such that the upper set of three rows move at a slower speed than the lower set, and consists in the illusory enhancement of the difference in velocity between the two rows adjacent to the velocity discontinuity.

METHOD

Fig. 1. (A) Figure modified after Benary (1924). (B) White's (1979) effect.

In both cases, the superficial analogy between the velocity effects and their brightness counterparts has been extended by the suggestion that similar physiological mechanisms underlie the two sets of phenomena. When it comes to motion, these mechanisms have been instantiated in the form of local processes of lateral inhibition between channels sensitive to velocity. Now, since these very same local contrast processes have been proved somehow inadequate in the realm of brightness, we are left with the question of whether they still hold true in the realm of velocity.

In this paper, a rough velocity-domain analogue of White's grating is described. Surprisingly (or perhaps not) the pattern gives rise to an illusion which closely resembles the one originated by its brightness-domain counterpart.

Configurations of moving dots were produced using an Iris 3130 graphics workstation and displayed on a 19-in. color monitor.

Individual stimulus patterns consisted of two separate sets of three horizontal rows each (see Fig. 2). There were 18 dots in each row, at a distance of 1.5 deg of visual angle from each other, and 37 min separated neighboring rows within a set. (Dots were actually small squares with a side of about 6 min.) The centers of the upper and lower sets were separated vertically by 9.2 deg. Within one set of three rows, the dots of the first and third rows (flanking rows) had the same color and moved with the same velocity a . The central row consisted of three separate sections; the dots of the left and right sections (collinear rows, 7 dots each) had the same color as the flanking rows' dots and moved with velocity b . The dots of the central section (test row, 4 dots) had a different color and moved with velocity c . The upper and lower sets were identical except for the fact that assignment of velocities to the contextual rows would always be reversed: so if flanking and collinear rows traveled respectively with velocities a and b in the upper set, they would travel respectively with velocities b and a in the lower set, and vice versa.

Dots were programed to move horizontally at a constant speed across the screen; whenever a dot disappeared at one end of the screen a new dot appeared on the other end, giving the impression of a continuous stream of moving elements. This was also true inside each of the three windows into which the central rows were split. Velocities a and b were fixed at 3 and 9 deg/sec respectively. The velocities of the test rows were varied across trials, and were either 6 deg/sec, or slightly more or slightly less. More precisely, the velocity of the test row flanked by slow-speed rows could be equal to the velocity

Fig. 2. Schematic illustration of the configuration used in the experiment. The arrows represent the velocities of the dots. Although the solid dots of the upper set and of the lower set are moving with the same velocity, the former appear to be moving faster. See text for description of the actual display.

of the test row flanked by high-speed rows (in which case they were both set at 6 deg/sec); 18 or 36 min/sec lower; or 18, 36 or 54 min/sec higher. All differences were generated as symmetrical departures from 6 deg/sec (e.g. a difference of 18 min/sec corresponded to actual velocities of 351 and 369 min/sec). During an experimental session, each of the six cases was presented 20 times; for 10 times the slow-speed flanking rows were in the upper set and for the other 10 times they were in the lower set. The order was randomized. The direction of motion was the same for all rows in a particular display; to prevent adaptation, directions were programmed to be either leftward or rightward, alternating between trials.

Four naive volunteers with normal visual acuity served as subjects. Two separate sessions of 120 trials each were run on each subject on consecutive days. The two sessions were in all respects identical except for the colors of the moving dots. In one of the sessions, each display had either green test dots and red contextual dots or vice versa (in random order across trials); in the other session, red was replaced by yellow. The background was always dark gray.

Observers were asked to compare the apparent velocity of the two test rows and to report which row appeared to be moving faster. They made judgments by pushing the appropriate mouse button; after each button press, the screen was cleared and a new display was presented. No fixation point was provided; observers were instructed to look back and forth between the two test rows, starting from each one about half of the time. The eye-screen distance was 60 cm.

RESULTS

A repeated-measures ANOVA was performed with color (green/red vs green/yellow), position (slow-speed rows in the upper vs lower set) and velocity difference between test rows (six levels of Δv) serving as factors. Statistical significance was reached only by the main effect of Δv [$F(5,15) = 29.08$, $P < 0.001$] and by the interaction between color and Δv [$F(5,15) = 3.08$, $P < 0.05$]. This interaction was (marginally) significant because the green/yellow condition yielded slightly higher means than the green/red condition for all values of Δv but one: when Δv was zero, things went the opposite way.

In Fig. 3, the data have been averaged across observers, positions and colors. This figure

Fig. 3. Frequency of "faster" responses to the test row with fast flanking rows as a function of Δv . Δ represents the velocity of the test row with slow flanking rows minus the velocity of the test row with fast flanking rows.

shows the frequency of responses "faster" to the test row flanked by high-speed rows as a function of the velocity differences between the two test rows. Negative values of Δv mean that the test row which subjects chose as faster was actually faster; positive values mean that the test row which subjects chose as faster was actually slower. If observers were basing their choices on the physical velocity difference between the test rows, the distribution should look symmetrical about the point of intersection of the two dashed lines (which represents equal probability of picking one or the other test row when they have the same speed). Note that instead the distribution is heavily asymmetrical, indicating that the test row flanked by high-speed rows was judged faster much more often. This test row looked faster not only when it was actually as fast as the other ($\Delta v = 0$: $z = 10.45$, $P < 0.0001$), but even when it was actually slower ($\Delta v = 18$: $z = 5.70$, $P < 0.0001$). The intersect of the curve with the 50% dashed line shows that the velocity difference between the two rows had to be at least 36 min/sec for them to be perceived as traveling at the same speed.

DISCUSSION

As mentioned in the Introduction, a mechanism of lateral inhibition between motion-sensitive cells has been suggested to explain the dependence of the apparent velocity of a target on the velocity of its immediate surround. When applied to the illusion presented here, however, the lateral inhibition hypothesis would imply

that a set of moving dots surrounded by more fast dots than slow dots should appear to move slower. Therefore the target flanked by the fast rows ought to be perceived as traveling at a lower speed, whereas the opposite is the case.

One could of course invoke some sort of orientational specificity of velocity-sensitive channels and claim that the test dots are being affected by the collinear elements only. This would still allow one to ascribe the illusion to inhibitory interactions within rows. I very much doubt this is the right track. A closer exploration of the effect is in progress, and suggests that only a mild contrast effect is observed when the flanking rows are removed. The flanking rows are therefore necessary for the effect to occur; whether they also are sufficient is currently being investigated.

All in all, it seems one should not hesitate to consider the phenomenon described in this article as an instance of velocity assimilation. Unlike velocity contrast, velocity assimilation does not appear to have been reported previously. It is within reason to assume that the two phenomena are separate manifestations of the interaction between neighboring motion-sensitive mechanisms. If it will be confirmed that

velocity contrast and assimilation are both at work in the display investigated in this paper, chances are that the two processes exhibit fundamentally different spatial characteristics. What these characteristics are, more research will hopefully tell.

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